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Integrating Regulating Ecosystem Services in Marine Conservation Planning

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally protected areas are designed to support the conservation of threatened species, habitats, and biodiversity. To also properly safeguard ecosystem functioning and services, protected area siting should consider more dimensions when moving towards the 30% protection targets. All species are not equal in terms of the ecosystem services they deliver, and e.g., carbon sequestration studies have focused on few species and habitats. The present study identifies key areas important for the conservation of regulating ecosystem service supply, by also considering species-specific traits such as size, lifespan, and growth form. We used an extensive data set covering over 170,000 observations of underwater marine diversity including algae, macrophytes and fauna, to produce maps on the spatial distribution of regulating services, including bioremediation and filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation of wastes and nutrients by algae, macrophytes and fauna, control of erosion and flooding, oxygen production and carbon sequestration and storage. We further identified key ecosystem service areas and optimal areas for increasing the protection of ecosystem services. The current marine protected area network covers only 24% of the service supply of the investigated services on average, but already with one well-targeted percentage point increase the service features covered would almost triple. The identified key ecosystem service areas and expansion candidates highlight the critical role of shallow coastal ecosystems and adjacent reef areas in supporting ecosystem service supply. The identified key areas are likely important for cultural services, with much of the human pressures focused close to shore, highlighting the need for further investigations into trade-offs between services and protected areas.

1 | Introduction

Linkages between people and nature are increasingly acknowledged in recent political agendas to ensure sustainable use of resources and address the current biodiversity crisis (Beery

et al. 2023). With the adoption of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) (CBD) in 2022, countries are now developing their protected area networks to meet the ambitious targets set for conservation. Target 3 of the GBF states that at least 30% of

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land and sea areas should be reserved for conservation by 2030, also highlighting areas with importance for ecosystem functions and services (CBD 2022).

According to the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), ecosystem services fall into three main categories: (1) regulating and maintenance, (2) provisioning and (3) cultural services (Haines-Young and Potschin 2018). Ecosystem services are deeply intertwined within a socio-ecological system and sometimes intangible, and therefore, difficult to quantify. Mapping and quantifying ecosystem services are also spatially complex exercises, as information are needed not only on where services occur (supply), but also where services are needed and used (demand). A recent review suggests that studies focusing on ecosystem service demand are still rare and regulating services are less frequently measured as actual flows (Czucz et al. 2020). In general, the ecosystem's capacity to provide services is considered to rely on the extent of the ecosystem (e.g., habitat, species range) and its condition (UN 2021). The relative contribution of species to supply ecosystem services is assumed to depend on species commonness (e.g., Winfree et al. 2015, but see Dee et al. 2019), i.e., how widely a species occurs, its abundance and population size and species functional traits, such as body size or feeding habit (de Bello et al. 2010; Hanisch et al. 2020). Quantifying ecosystem services should rely on information on species biomass and rates, but in practice, only data on species occurrences are usually available, especially in the marine realm (Galparsoro et al. 2021).

Ecosystem services have broadened the traditional, rather ecologically centred view of conservation, where not only nature but also ecosystem services are integrated in protected area design (Villarreal-Rosas et al. 2020). Conservation practices, as directed by various conservation policies, are mainly targeted towards threatened species and habitats, at the cost of species not (yet) of conservation concern (Virtanen and Moilanen 2023). This focus also means that conservation planning, in general, concentrates on finding suitable sites for protecting species and habitats at risk of extinction (Moura et al. 2013; Jones et al. 2020). Ecosystem services are rarely the sole motivation for area-based conservation, as policies have not (yet) required such (Pu et al. 2023).

Previous studies that have identified the most important areas for protecting ecosystem services (Pu et al. 2023), evaluated overlaps between ecosystem services and protected areas (Mitchell et al. 2021), assessed the capacity of ecosystems to deliver benefits to people (Daw et al. 2016) and integrated functional traits in ecosystem service provisioning (Schibalski et al. 2022). Examples where marine protected areas (MPAs) and their locations would have been designed based on the provisioning of ecosystem services are much rarer (Arkema et al. 2024), especially regarding regulating services. Some studies have investigated ecosystem service benefits of MPAs (Potts et al. 2014; Geange et al. 2019; Duarte et al. 2024), but there are gaps in the type of habitats considered, and a clear need to assess ecosystem services quantitatively, as highlighted in, e.g. Ruskule et al. (2023) and Arkema et al. (2024). In the marine realm, provisioning services, both supply and demand, can be linked to marine resources, such as fisheries

and extractive uses, like seabed mining, while regulating services such as oxygen production and bioremediation are more difficult to quantify spatially.

Here, we develop conservation scenarios to progress towards GBF Target 3 on increasing the protection of ecosystem functions and services. We quantify seven regulating and maintenance services by combining information on species distributions and traits (e.g., life span, biovolume and biomass), relying on extensive marine biodiversity and trait data from the northern Baltic Sea. Using spatial conservation prioritization, we identify important areas for the delivery of ecosystem services, while also considering service demand and determining potential MPA expansion candidate sites to increase ecosystem service protection.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Study Area

Our study area covers Finnish territorial waters and the exclusive economic zone, located in the northern Baltic Sea. The area covers 81,500 km² of shallow waters (mean depth 48 m), with tens of thousands of islands and skerries. Finnish marine areas host relatively few species of limnic and marine origin that have adapted to brackish conditions (salinity 0–6), and a relatively long ice season (Forsblom et al. 2024). Coastal areas suffer from eutrophication and recurrent hypoxia, together with various human activities (Korpinen et al. 2012; Virtanen et al. 2019). This ecologically simple system, with a relatively low number of species, provides an excellent opportunity to quantify ecosystem services and ways to promote their protection.

2.2 | Overall Workflow

In this study, we quantified regulating ecosystem services to be further used in spatial prioritization to identify important sites for the protection of ecosystem services. Our workflow consisted of several steps: first, we produced species distribution models based on comprehensive species observations. Then, we assigned ecosystem services to the species based on previously published literature reviews and estimated the contribution of species to services based on their traits. Finally, we used spatial prioritization to define areas important for ecosystem services conservation. The workflow is presented in Figure 1 and the steps are described in more detail in the following chapters.

2.3 | Biodiversity Data

We used a comprehensive marine biodiversity dataset, to date collected from over 190,000 sites located in Finnish marine waters (Forsblom et al. 2024). The data used include species percentage cover (%) and mean heights (cm) for algae and macrophytes, collected mainly through scientific diving and video observation methods, as well as information on invertebrate biomass, based on benthic surveys (see details in Forsblom et al. 2024). Biomass data for the benthic fauna was extracted from the POHJE database.

I) Species distribution models (SDM) for algae, macrophytes, and macrofauna are produced based on extensive biodiversity data.

II) Species are assigned to regulating ecosystem services based on a previously published literature review.

III a) Traits are estimated to affect the contribution of species to services. Traits considered are biovolume (flora) or biomass (fauna), lifespan & association with sediment.

III b) Biovolume and biomass are modelled based on SDMs and available data. Then, based on literature, other traits are used to weigh these maps.

IV) The trait-weighted species maps are summed to produce ecosystem service maps (separately for flora and fauna).

V) Key ecosystem service areas are identified using spatial prioritization.

FIGURE 1 | Description of the workflow showing (I) how species distribution models are created based on extensive biodiversity dataset; (II) how each species model is linked (lines) from the habitat (left) to the services (right); (III) how depending on the ecosystem service, the species-specific traits have different weights and how the species-specific maps (IV) are summed to produce the final ecosystem service maps; (V) subsequently used for identifying key ecosystem service areas using spatial prioritization.

2.4 | Species Models

We used Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) (Elith et al. 2008), which is a decision tree-based machine learning approach, to model the probability of species occurrence for 55 algae, 37 macrophytes, and 18 fauna. We trained the models with 70% of the data ($n = 1077-86,837$) and left 30% ($n = 462-38,205$) out for validation, assessed by area under the curve operator (AUC). We used a bag fraction of 0.7, meaning that 70% of the training data are drawn at random (without replacement) at each iteration, and chose other hyperparameters, learning rate (0.1, 0.01, 0.001) and tree complexity (2,3,5), based on the lowest root mean squared error. The learning rate determines the contribution of each tree to model building, while tree complexity defines how interactions are fitted. Of the considered covariates, the most important ones included salinity, depth, substrate, turbidity and openness, which previously have been considered important for modelling species distributions in the area (Virtanen et al. 2018, 2024). The models were used to make spatial predictions of occurrence probability for each species across the whole Finnish sea area. A full description of the modelling and list of variables is described in Supplement 2.

2.5 | Ecosystem Services

To connect individual species and their contribution to ecosystem services, we used a recent literature review (Jernberg et al. 2024) that links northern Baltic Sea habitats to ecosystem services. We consider seven regulating services

classified according to the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES, <https://cices.eu/>), hereafter referred to as in the parenthesis:

1. Bioremediation of wastes by algae, macrophytes and fauna (*bioremediation*)
2. Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by algae, macrophytes and fauna for harmful substances (*toxins*)
3. Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by algae, macrophytes and fauna for nutrients (*nutrients*)
4. Control of erosion rates (*erosion*)
5. Flood control, and coastal protection (*flood*)
6. Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes (only net oxygen production considered) (*oxygen*)
7. Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans (i.e., carbon sequestration and storage) (*carbon*)

Harmful substances and nutrients were analysed separately, even though in CICES they belong to the same service class; see Jernberg et al. (2024) for details.

2.6 | Species Traits

The supply of ecosystem services is influenced by traits and some traits are associated with enhanced ecosystem service production, whereas others might lead to no discernible effect (de

Bello et al. 2010). We focused on three traits: species biomass (or biovolume), lifespan of species, and whether the species is associated with soft sediment type. Size or biomass of species is expected to contribute to ecosystem service production in general; the bigger the biomass, the more the species can store carbon and nutrients, produce oxygen and, for example, mitigate the effects of erosion. Lifespan influences the stability of services and the longer species live, the slower the turnover of carbon and nutrients and thus release back to biogeochemical cycling or the atmosphere (Becker et al. 2010; Gallagher et al. 2021). For example, annual algae are not considered to contribute to services such as carbon storage here. Macrophyte association with soft sediments and the belowground biomass, such as rhizomes and roots in *Zostera* habitats, can contribute to carbon storage by stabilizing the sediment (Röhr et al. 2016). Similarly, infauna species are tied to sediment-rich areas that can also be high in carbon (see references in de Bello et al. 2010).

We used two approaches to include traits in the ecosystem services models. First, we estimated species biovolume (for flora) based on height and cover and biomass (for fauna) from the available biodiversity data. Then we used literature to estimate the contribution of lifespan and sediment to specific services.

We accounted for the estimated size of the algae and macrophytes by multiplying the predicted species occurrence probabilities with species height (cm) and cover (%) estimates, using the top 95th percentile values to produce biovolume estimates (maps). For faunal species, we estimated the biomass by multiplying the occurrence probability with the top 95th percentile of wet weight measures for each species (Figure 2). Traits including canopy height and biomass contribute positively to many services (Lammerant, Norkko, et al. 2024; Lammerant, Rohlfers, et al. 2024). As biomass values were only available for fauna, we used biovolume to account for the size and complexity of the vegetation.

Lifespan and species association with sediment were selected based on literature (Table 1, Figure 2). Lifespan information was mainly based on Törnroos and Bonsdorff (2012), and we classified all fauna as either short- or long-lived. The lifespan of the vegetation was based on Blomqvist et al. (2014) and Viitasalo et al. (2021). Infauna and macrophytes with roots were considered to have enhanced production of certain services due to the

association with sediments and otherwise considered to contribute neutrally.

2.7 | Ecosystem Service Maps

The ecosystem service maps were produced by multiplying the species-specific map layers of biovolume (flora) or biomass (fauna) with the weighted trait information of species lifespan and sediment association. The species-specific maps were

FIGURE 2 | The top 95th percentile values for cover, height, and wet weight (g WW/m²) for each considered habitat type. Some habitats include only one species.

TABLE 1 | The weights used to link the ecosystem services to the species. The values are multiplied with the relevant species models to produce weighted species traits.

	Lifespan			Sediment habitat	
	Annual/Short	Biennial/Short lived perennial	Perennial/Long	No	Yes
Bioremediation	1	1	1	1	1
Oxygen	1	1	1	1	1
Nutrients	0	1	2	1	2
Toxins	0	1	2	1	2
Carbon	0	1	2	1	2
Erosion	0	1	1	1	2
Flood	0	1	1	1	2

coupled to their habitat type and subsequently to ecosystem services based on identified connections in Jernberg et al. (2024) (supplement), keeping flora and fauna separate. For erosion and flood protection services, we identified areas with demand for the service based on the most recent CORINE land cover data product (Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) 2018). We considered areas within a distance of 200m with sandy shores to benefit from erosion protection (Bozzeda et al. 2023), and shore areas within 200m with urban and agricultural land use to benefit from flood protection (Wübbelmann et al. 2023). The maps were then summed, resulting in one layer for each ecosystem service for flora and fauna, further used as input in the spatial prioritization analysis used to identify key ecosystem service areas described in the next section.

2.8 | Spatial Conservation Prioritization

Spatial prioritization is the technical part of systematic conservation planning and is commonly used in identifying priority areas for conservation actions (see Giakoumi et al. 2025 and references therein). Spatial prioritization integrates spatial data on biodiversity (e.g., species distributions, habitats), ecosystem services, pressures from human activities, as well as costs and administrative units (e.g., protected areas) (Kujala et al. 2018). We used spatial prioritization as implemented by the Zonation 5 v2.1 software (Moilanen et al. 2022) to (i) identify important areas for regulating ecosystem services, (ii) evaluate how well they are currently protected by the Finnish MPA network, and finally, (iii) where to increase their conservation. Zonation has previously been used in, e.g. ecologically informed land and sea use planning (e.g., Virtanen et al. 2022; Jalkanen et al. 2025), identifying sites for conservation (e.g., Mikkonen et al. 2023; Kujala et al. 2023; Eckert et al. 2023) and impact avoidance (Kareksela et al. 2013).

Zonation produces a spatial priority rank map, where grid cells in the seascape are ranked in order of conservation importance, based on an iterative optimization algorithm. In high-ranked areas (close to 1) the loss of each grid cell would lead to greater aggregate losses for biodiversity, while the low-ranked sites (close to 0) hold lower value (e.g., ecologically deteriorated areas). Zonation also produces feature-specific performance curves that link to the spatial priority rank map, which tell the coverage of features in any chosen fraction of the seascape. Zonation has multiple options for ranking, i.e., how the marginal loss from the removal of grid cells is calculated (see details in Moilanen et al. 2022). We used Core Area Zonation, CAZ2, to emphasize relatively high average coverage of features (Moilanen et al. 2022). We set equal positive weights ($w=1$) for all ecosystem services. In general, changing the weights for some species (or, in this case, ecosystem services) or adding new data in multi-species spatial prioritization has limited impact on site value the more data is included in the analysis (e.g., > 100 species) (Kujala et al. 2018). We opted for an objective, balanced prioritization result to reveal core areas for ecosystem services. Therefore, there was no justification for elevating or demoting weights of any of the services considered.

We first developed a prioritization scenario where we identified key areas for ecosystem service delivery, and then another

scenario to evaluate where to increase the protection of these key areas. To do this, we used hierarchic analysis, in which the priority ranking is developed constrained by the present MPA network (e.g., Mikkonen and Moilanen 2013; Virtanen et al. 2018). The analysis allows identification of those areas outside the MPA network, which would increase conservation coverage of ecosystem services in a balanced and area-efficient manner. With the analysis, we were also able to evaluate how well the present MPA network currently protects ecosystem service delivery. In the results, we present rank maps and their performance curves, i.e., the coverage of individual ecosystem services in each (protected) sea fraction, as well as histograms of ecosystem service coverages. The base fraction considered is 11% that corresponds to the current MPA cover, with additional fractions covering expansions of 1%, 5%, 10% and 19%, which correspond to a total sea area cover of 12%, 17%, 22% and 30%. We also show the depth profile and distance from shore of the current MPA network with the ideal network for enhanced ecosystem services delivery to further illustrate how the areas are distributed close to shore vs. offshore.

3 | Results

3.1 | Species Distribution

All species distribution models performed satisfactorily based on validation with the training data set and AUC values calculated from validation data exceeded 0.82 (mean 0.95) for all species. Visual inspection of the change in residual deviance as the number of trees increased also indicated good model convergence. The most important variables explaining the distribution of species included salinity, seabed substrate and temperature (details in Data S1). Including information on biomass, biovolume and traits enabled us to produce more realistic maps where the contribution of each species varied by its size. The maps of each service are shown in Figures S1–S11.

3.2 | High-Priority Areas for Ecosystem Services and Increasing Their Protection

We evaluated how well the present MPA network protects ecosystem services based on the produced maps of species volume and their contribution to ecosystem services. The priority rank map in Figure 3A show the most valuable areas for ecosystem services across Finnish marine areas. Most uniform and largest high-priority areas are located closer to shore or further out in reef areas in the Bothnian Sea, around the outer edges of the Archipelago Sea and Gulf of Finland. Considering the areas already protected, the largest MPA expansion areas are in the Archipelago Sea, along with some smaller areas in the northern Bothnian Sea and Gulf of Finland (Figure 3B).

In an ideal situation if an MPA network would have been designed from scratch, corresponding to the 11% presently protected, on average, a 62% coverage of ecosystem services would have been achieved (Figure 4A). In this scenario, erosion control would be almost completely protected, over 90% of flood protection covered and 52% of carbon and 50% of bioremediation services conserved.

FIGURE 3 | (A) High priority areas for ecosystem services in Finland's marine areas and (B) where to increase protection of ecosystem services, considering the existing MPA network.

However, as MPAs have already been established (11% of the Finnish marine areas), they protect, on average 24% of the ecosystem service supply (Figure 4A), ranging from 19% (flood) to 37% (erosion) for individual ecosystem services (Figure 4B). Selecting the highest ranked areas of the priority rank map in Figure 3B would be the best candidates for expanding the present MPA network based on ecosystem service supply. Expanding the current MPAs by a well-chosen 1% point would almost triple the coverage of ecosystem services to 70%, and with a 5% point expansion, on average, 75% of ecosystem services would be protected (Figure 4A). The key message from Figure 4B is that expanding the protected area network for ecosystem services is more efficient for erosion and flood control, as with only a 1%-point increase, both would be almost fully covered. Interestingly, for carbon, the protected area network would need much higher coverage—protecting 30% of Finnish marine areas would render ~75% of carbon to be conserved.

When looking closer into how the selected areas (Figure 3) are distributed along depth and distance to shore gradients, to compare the 11% of the current network and the ideal solution, three depth zones stand out (Figure 5), with very shallow, and around 10 and 20 m. Further looking at the 1%-point increase to the current MPA networks, new areas are especially needed in shallow littoral areas. The distribution on a coastal to open water

gradient is more similar with the current 11% cover (Figure 5B), but similarly as with depth the majority of the expansion percentage is located close to shore.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | Protection of Regulating Ecosystem Services

We identified key areas for the supply of regulating ecosystem services and evaluated how well they are currently protected, and where their protection should be increased. At present, 11% of the Finnish marine area is to some extent protected. However, over two thirds of ecosystem service supply offered by aquatic vegetation and fauna falls outside of this area, as suggested by the present study. We found that increasing the cover of protected areas by 1% point (815km²) could triple the protection of the regulating services investigated here. While the real-life expansion of MPAs might be challenging due to conflicting sea uses or ownership of the areas, accounting for ecosystem services when considering MPAs can produce added value (Sala et al. 2021). Conservation policies typically focus on rare species and habitats threatened with extinction (e.g., the IUCN Red List). Introducing additional criteria, such as promoting the delivery of ecosystem services, could provide incentives for protecting species not (yet) threatened. Marine spatial planning,

FIGURE 4 | (A) Mean fraction of ecosystem services covered within the present MPA network (green lines) and in the ideal scenario (orange lines), and fractions of sea area protected shown in dotted vertical lines. (B) Mean fraction of ecosystem services covered in both scenarios, corresponding to the level currently protected of marine areas (11%), and with a 1%-, 5%-, 10%-, and 19%-point increase to MPA network. The fraction of ecosystem services covered at each fraction sea area protected corresponds to y-axis in A, and vertical dotted lines correspond to increase alternatives.

FIGURE 5 | Density curves for depth (A) and distance from shore (B) for the current MPA network cover of 11% and for a 1%-point expansion. Current and ideal MPA network indicated by colours. Note difference in y-axis for panels.

which guides the allocation of human activities and therefore minimizes potential harmful impacts on ecosystems, could also support the maintenance of ecosystem services.

The current MPA network primarily protects deeper and more exposed areas that do not necessarily constitute key areas for the protection of the supply of the services considered here, suggesting

that there is some inefficiency in the present network from an ecosystem service perspective. Similar inefficiencies have been highlighted in the preservation of protected species and biodiversity (Virtanen et al. 2018). Reasons for this inefficiency are twofold: First, the locations of the present MPA network reflect mainly the information available at the time MPAs were established, protecting habitats, bird areas or even terrestrial nature on islands. Prior knowledge of underwater conservation values was not available at the time. Second, a large part of MPAs in Finland has been established on government-owned waters located further offshore in deeper areas, while valuable areas for ecosystem services and for biodiversity (e.g., Virtanen et al. 2018) mainly occur in privately owned shallow coastal areas. Increasing the protection in these areas requires extensive awareness raising and collaboration, as conservation needs to be voluntary.

4.2 | Key Areas for Ecosystem Services

Our results show a dichotomy of key priority areas for ecosystem services. Many of the key areas identified were either in shallow photic areas closer to shore and in sheltered bays, determined by light availability, or on the other hand, further offshore on deeper reef areas. These results are not surprising, as the depth distribution of vegetation is mainly limited by light availability, and the photic zone in Finland is rather narrow (Lappalainen et al. 2019). Therefore, shallow coastal areas tend to be biodiversity hotspots, but these areas are also exposed to pressures and recreational land use (Hansen et al. 2019; Virtanen et al. 2024). The very same areas also provide nurseries for commercially important fish (Sundblad and Bergström 2014) and carbon sequestration (Sala et al. 2021).

Defining not only the service supply, but also the areas where services are most beneficial for people (e.g., as erosion and flood protection) is crucial. In our example, areas where services were 'needed', were much more detailed and spatially confined. In the ranking, this elevates the aggregate marginal loss of these areas, and therefore they are much easier to protect, which can be seen from the fast increase in protection coverage in the performance curves (Figure 4A). Also, fauna was not considered to contribute to the abovementioned services and to oxygen production. Increasing the protection of other services such as nutrient regulation was likely slower due to the broader distribution of these services compared to erosion and flood protection and because many of the considered faunal species such as polychaete worms have a much broader depth distribution than vegetation.

4.3 | Expanding the Criteria for Marine Conservation

CBD has set targets for protecting carbon-rich habitats, and at least within the scope of the habitats presented here, increasing their protection will be challenging. Even with a 5%-point increase, barely half of the estimated extent of the habitats tied to carbon sequestration and storage will be accounted for. This result stems from the fact that these habitats are rather widespread and common, but the key areas they form together for ecosystem services do not form uniform, distinct areas. It is also important to expand the view on traditional carbon-rich habitats. Even if we

included two habitats well known for their importance to carbon storage and sequestration, i.e., seagrass meadows and coastal wetlands, studies have highlighted the importance of aphotic soft sediment sea floors (James et al. 2024), and the fact that almost all carbon is tied to the non-living stock (Scheffold and Hense 2020). Here we only considered the biotic habitat types, but the extent of muddy sediments far outweighs the extent of, e.g., seagrass meadows in the study area (Virtanen and Forsblom et al. 2024). These sediments are likely substantial carbon storages and could play a key role in climate change mitigation (e.g., Epstein et al. 2025). Protecting the carbon storage of muddy sediments through area-based conservation may not always be the most effective approach, unless measures are also taken to regulate activities that disturb the seabed, such as dredging, which can stir the sediments and release stored carbon.

4.4 | The Role of Species and Their Traits in the Delivery of Ecosystem Services

When assessing ecosystem service supply, many species can offer the same service, highlighting the importance of abundance (Winfrey et al. 2015) and functional redundancy as part of stability and the insurance hypothesis sensu Yachi and Loreau (1999), where other species can compensate for a lost species in terms of sustaining functions/services. Many important services are offered by widely distributed species, such as the carbon storage and sequestration offered by coastal habitats dominated by the common reed *Phragmites australis* (Buczko et al. 2022), or the ability to stabilize sediment, which can be offered by a broad range of aquatic vegetation (Temmerman et al. 2013; Karimi et al. 2022). Some common habitats and species can also have a negative effect on conservation efforts if they are linked to eutrophication and outcompete or overgrow other species and habitats (Altartouri et al. 2014). For example, while reed beds sequester and store carbon efficiently (Buczko et al. 2022), they are also known to expand aggressively and could outcompete and displace other species (Pitkänen et al. 2013) and threaten habitats with overgrowth, including endangered habitats such as flads that provide nurseries for many fish species (Pursiainen et al. 2021; Westerborn et al. 2023).

Incorporating information on species traits or abundance into siting of MPAs can influence the outcome of conservation actions. For example, Vercaemmen et al. (2019) showed that considering reef area, but ignoring coral cover, could overestimate the conservation benefit by up to 62%. In our study, including traits describing species volume and biomass improved the ecological realism of our assessment by giving higher weight to areas where species that are functionally more important for specific services occur. Ideally, we would use information on rates for specific services, such as species-specific carbon sequestration or oxygen production. This kind of information is rarely available or known only for a small subset of species, and when available, varies spatio-temporally (Röhr et al. 2016) so that extrapolating between sites or countries could be ill advised. In contrast, species-specific trait information can be more readily available compared to information on rates and thus a good option for other studies. This approach could be more easily adapted to areas where data is scarce as it aims to identify the most important areas for ecosystem services supply instead

of trying to estimate the exact volumes of service production. Future studies could expand on this concept by including more traits that characterize processes, such as nutrient uptake or consider broader trait clusters (Schibalski et al. 2022).

4.5 | Future Outlook

Considering the recent pace at which marine ecosystems are changing, it can be plausibly assumed that the supply of ecosystem services will also change and shift drastically as species are tracking their climatic niche (Lenoir et al. 2020). These changes are not necessarily in concordance with the demand for ecosystem services that most likely increases in the near future with the triple crises of climate change, biodiversity loss and the unsustainability of food production (IPBES nexus report, McElwee et al. 2025). The need for ecosystem services also depends on the development of coastal areas, such as land use and urbanization, thus affecting the geographic and distribution patterns of ecosystem service demand. In our example, southern parts of the Bothnian Sea are important for ecosystem service delivery at present, although their conservation value may change in the future if species contributing to ecosystem services are not able to survive with the predicted impacts of changing climate. Thus, there is a need to develop adaptive conservation strategies that are able to track the pace ecosystems change (Rilov et al. 2020). Other human pressures can also influence the ability of habitats to produce services. For example, in the Mediterranean Sea, the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica* contributes more to sediment carbon stock of pristine areas compared to urban areas (Mazarrasa et al. 2017). This can create a conflict of interest where multiple priorities need to be balanced and considered.

4.6 | Conclusions

The present identification of ecosystem service supply should be seen as a supplement to analyses that identify conservation areas based on biodiversity and the presence of endangered species. Increasing the cover of protected areas by just 1% point could triple the amount of ecosystem service features, so choosing expansion candidates carefully is crucial and could produce added value by also protecting ecosystem services.

The identified areas not only highlight the importance of shallow coastal areas in supporting abundant life but also from an ecosystem service perspective. Both shallow coastal areas and adjacent reef areas are important for safeguarding ecosystem services. As many of the key areas identified overlap with recreational use (Paulus et al. 2024) and the outer areas with commercial interests, such as offshore wind power development (Virtanen et al. 2022), further investigations into trade-offs between ecosystem service supply, sea use and protected areas are urgently needed.

Author Contributions

Louise Forsblom: writing – review and editing, writing – original draft (lead), visualization, formal analysis, conceptualization (lead). **Susanna Jernberg:** writing – review and editing, conceptualization (supporting). **Harri Kuosa:** writing – review and editing. **Kirsi Kostamo:** writing – review and editing. **Camilla Gustafsson:** writing

– review and editing. **Elina A. Virtanen:** writing – review and editing, writing – original draft, visualization, formal analysis, conceptualization (lead).

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Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The species data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822191>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.